

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PURCHASING BEHAVIOUR OF YOUNG CONSUMERS TOWARD SUSTAINABLE HANDICRAFT PRODUCTS

Neha Agarwal^{1*}, Madhulika Gautam²

Research Scholar¹, Professor²

^{1&2}Dayalbagh Educational Institute (Deemed to be University), Dayalbagh, Agra, UP, India, 282005

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to analyse about the relation in the influencing factors involved in constructing consumers' behaviour, especially of youngsters those are involved in purchasing handicraft products. The study was conducted on 234 respondents from Uttar Pradesh, aged 16-40 years selected using a Snow ball sampling method. Findings revealed that consumers' behaviour was positively related to various influential factors such as the opinion of friends and family most, functional value, status, aesthetic value, and purchasing methods. The consumers' age positively impacted consumer behaviour, tested by regression coefficient ($b = .118$, $R^2 = .085$, $p < .001$). The study also analysed that the consumers aged 35-40 years and the consumers with annual family income under the above 5 Lac rupees category had a higher impact on consumer behaviour which was depicted by ANOVA ($F = 8.73, 10.81, p < .001$) respectively. In addition, various factors influence consumers in purchasing of handicraft products. The future generation can be aware about the value of ecofriendly products by the current generation as it represents the Indian culture. Availability of eco-friendly products can be seen as competitive products through exhibitions.

Keywords: Buying behaviour, Handicraft products, Influencing factors, Sustainable, Young consumers

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Handicraft products are developed by hands or by using some hand tools. In ancient time, handicraft products were designed as a hobby or as a group activity to use their time. It represents a particular heritage and the culture of that time. Developing handicraft products can reconnect people with its ancient period and it is the unique method to preserve own long-standing culture Shaikh (2020); Tiwari (2015). In India, Handicraft sector is the second largest economic sector after agriculture for livelihood. Handicraft sector is low in energy consumption and environment friendly, as noted by Dhingra & Dhingra (2012). This sector has faced various issues after industrial revolution like competition in market, limited awareness about market, regular changes in consumers choices. Indian handicraft has to resolve these issues by maintaining its uniqueness, worth and glory without losing its global recognition. It is essential to analyse the consumer behaviour to promote and sustain handicraft market. It includes hand-knotted rugs, embroidered and crocheted home decors, handcrafted jewellery, textiles, leather items, etc. Shaikh in 2020 resulted that consumer behaviour is different area wise as well for handicraft. In urban area the handicraft products are counted as luxurious and classical items whereas in rural areas, handicrafts are remarked as a legacy that is a sense of preserved ancient culture and their emotions are attached to it. Some factors are involved which influence consumer behaviour significantly. Kumar (2022); Prajapati & Uraon (2024) illustrated some major factors those influence consumer behaviour as psychological, economic, social, cultural and personal. When the functionality of the products is high then the demand of the products is also high. Dash (2011) noted that globally consumers like handicrafts and one of the reasons behind it are the feelings and emotions those are linked to the tradition and culture of particular region. More factors associated to make intention to purchase

these kinds of products. Thamrin et al. (2023) revealed that to increase the sale of handicraft, visibility of products is essential and it can be achieved by the use of digital platforms at present time. E-commerce initiatives can boost the economy as incorporated by Nepal government (Ngudup & Chen, 2005). Online platforms like Crafts Bazaar, Craftsvilla and Engrave are greater support to grow Indian handicraft market. Awareness of consumers about the products push the growth to this sector. The present study assesses the consumer's buying behaviour of handicrafts based on their age, income and other relevant factors. This study guides to understand the complex buying behaviour and the various attributes that make consumers' attitudes positive towards sustainable handicrafts. According to Pani and Pradhan (2016) understanding the consumer behaviour of different market segments supports sellers in choosing the best possible product design, pricing, advertising appeals, and distribution methods.

2.0 OBJECTIVES

- To study consumer behaviour towards buying sustainable handicraft products.
- To assess influential factors for buying sustainable handicraft products.
- To evaluate the significant factors influencing consumers' choices to buy sustainable handicrafts.

3.0 HYPOTHESIS

1. **h₁** Consumer behaviour and the variables influencing handicraft purchases are positively correlated.
2. **h₁** Age of consumers positively impacts consumer behaviour towards purchasing handicraft products.
3. **h₁** Annual family income of consumers positively impacts consumer behaviour for handicraft products purchasing.

4.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

4.1 Locale of the study and sample selection

This study is exploratory and conducted in Uttar Pradesh. A total of 234 willing respondents completed the questionnaire. Respondents were selected using the snowball sampling method. This method was more appropriate because of having large geographical area, easier way to collect data. All the respondents were from urban areas of Uttar Pradesh. Both males and females from >16 to <40 in age were participated in this study. Selecting both genders helped to cover deep analysis as both genders purchase handicraft products and avoided gender-based biasness in analysis. The selection of this age category is covering both economically dependent and independent respondents and this group is actively engaged in online shopping and more possibilities to participate in online survey.

4.2 Data collection

The research used a self-constructed questionnaire to collect data. The tool was covered in three sections. First section was used to cover the socio demographic profile. Second section included 3 items to cover the consumer behaviour towards buying eco-friendly products. Third section was used to cover about the factors those influence consumer's behaviour to buy sustainable handicraft products. Total 8 influencing factors were selected after reviewing the published articles. The selected factors are age, income, opinion of others, appearance, status, aesthetic value, functional value and purchasing method. Total 16 items were designed to cover all factors except age and income. 5point Likert scale was used for 2nd and 3rd section of the tool. The tool was framed in a Google form and delivered to the respondents through social platforms email, WhatsApp.

4.3 Variables

Two variables Independent and Dependent variables were identified for analysis and to describe clarity about consumer behaviour and the influencing factors those are involved in purchasing sustainable handicraft products.

Independent variables: Age, annual family income, opinion, appearance, status, aesthetic value, functional value, purchasing method,

Dependent variable: Consumer behaviour

4.4 Data analysis

The self-constructed tool in two sections was applied to collect the data. As it was framed in 5point Likert scale so strongly disagree was scored as the least number as 1 and strongly agree was scored as the highest scores as 5. SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 20 was used for statistical test as Mean, SD, Pearson's correlation, Coefficient regression and ANOVA. Cronbach's alpha was used to check the reliability of the questionnaire. A total of 19 items were used in the questionnaire to fulfill the research objectives, and got .945 scores which means the tool was highly reliable.

5.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 5.1. Assessment of Consumers' Behaviour and Influencing Factors for Buying Sustainable Handicraft Products

S. No.	Scale	Mean	SD
1.	Consumer behaviour toward buying handicrafts		
I	I sometimes buy handicrafts that I had not planned to acquire when I go shopping.	3.51	.96
II	I typically purchase handicrafts that truly catch my eye without considering consequences.	3.73	1.10
III	I frequently enjoy making impulsive purchases of handcrafted goods.	3.55	1.04
2.	Influential factors		
2. A.	Opinion matters.		
I	I purchase handicrafts that other people appreciate.	3.46	1.31
II	I consider the opinions of my friends and family before buying handicrafts.	3.54	1.06
III	Until my friends and family give their approval, I hardly ever buy any handicrafts.	3.26	1.17
IV	Whether or not I buy handcrafted goods is primarily up to me.	3.60	1.15
2. B.	Appearance		
I	I purchase handicrafts because I believe they appear more authentic than those made in factories.	3.91	1.11
II	I purchase them for their artistic value.	3.99	1.09
III	I purchase them for their appearance.	3.83	.99
2. C.	Social status		
I	I am able to buy sustainable handicrafts.	3.90	.97
II	Handicrafts are environmentally beneficial so I purchase them, no matter they are more expensive.	3.69	1.10
III	I want to have luxuries at home, so I purchase handicrafts.	3.64	1.15
2.D.	Functional value		

I	I purchase handicrafts because I am aware of the useful value they provide.	3.76	1.04
II	I purchase them because of their quality.	3.88	1.03
III	I would like to buy handicrafts for my friends, family, and others.	3.64	1.02
2. E.	Aesthetic value		
I	I purchase handicrafts because they are part of the culture of India.	3.86	1.11
2. F.	Purchasing method		
I	I prefer online platforms to buy handicrafts rather than offline.	3.28	1.11
2. G.	Overall preference		
		3.79	1.04

The above given table 1 elaborates about the several factors those impact on consumer behaviour for purchasing handicraft products. The mean values of all items related to consumers' buying behaviour were at agree level. The first section related to consumer behaviour toward buying handicrafts shows that consumers' purchase handicrafts because they find them eye catching with mean score 3.73 and purchase regularly which revealed by mean score 3.55 and another section also suggests that the selected influencing factors were in agree level that represents that these factors are linked to make consumers' behaviour in buying handicraft products. Customers take opinion of their friends and family before purchasing but they also care about their own choices and make final decision accordingly and it was cleared by the mean value 3.60 that is higher among all items of this factor. The factor appearance of the products scored as the highest mean value among all factors that indicates that this factor higher impact on buying decision. Customers praise the artistic value of handicraft products which is justifies with mean score 3.99 and with mean score 3.91, customers find the products more authentic. Customers' social status also effect on their behaviour as the mean score 3.90 and 3.69 indicates that customers buy handicraft because they are sustainable and eco-friendly respectively. Customers find luxurious features in

handicrafts. The functional value of the products is another factor to make decision to buy them. As customers purchase handicrafts because of their high quality and the mean score (3.88) represents their agreement with this fact. Most consumers were aware that handicrafts are the part of Indian culture and the mean score 3.86 reveals their agreement on this. The purchasing method also the major factor which impacts on making decision to buy handicrafts as today online market is widely used to purchase which provides easy access to worldwide market comfortably and the respondents were also liked this way to purchase handicrafts. It indicates that online selling of handicrafts give exposure worldwide to the artisans Pani & Pradhan (2016), also mentioned that the various factors like simplicity, aesthetic value, creativity, functional value and eco-friendliness influence customers to frame their buying behaviour for handicrafts. In last, the table reveals that in overall respondents preferred handicraft products higher, cleared with the mean value (3.79). The respondents agreed to give preference to handicraft products. Similarly, **Pani & Pradhan, 2016** also found a higher positive preference for handicraft products.

Table 5.2. Association of Consumer Behaviour and All Influential Factors Related to Handicraft Products (n=234)

	Variables	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1.	Consumer behaviour	10.79	2.48	-						
2.	Opinion	13.86	3.65	.66**	-					
3.	Appearance	11.73	2.74	.55**	.39**	-				
4.	Social status	11.23	2.79	.58**	.42**	.78**	-			
5.	Functional value	11.26	2.67	.62**	.53**	.84**	.82**	-		
6.	Aesthetic value	3.86	1.11	.56**	.45**	.82**	.74**	.76**	-	
7.	Purchasing method	3.28	1.11	.36**	.44**	.47**	.60**	.52**	.52**	-

** $p < .01$.

Table 2 above illustrates the association between consumer behaviour and the factors those influence product purchases, including opinions, product appearance, respondents' social status, functional value, aesthetic value, and purchasing method. It was revealed that the opinions of friends and family had a considerable impact on the purchasing intentions of consumers ($r = .66$, $p < .01$), the appearance of products ($r = .55$, $p < .01$), maintaining status ($r = .58$, $p < .01$), functional value of the products ($r = .62$, $p < .01$), aesthetic value of products ($r = .56$, $p < .01$), and purchasing methods ($r = .36$, $p < .01$). The findings reveals that all given influencing factors were highly related to each other in a positive way.

Pani & Pradhan (2016) and **Silver (2012)** also mentioned that the factors of opinion, appearance, and status are correlated to influence consumer behaviour.

Hypothesis 1

h1 Consumer behaviour and the variables influencing handicraft purchases are positively correlated.

The statistical evaluation indicates that there is approval for the framed alternative hypothesis because the test of Pearson correlation illustrates consumers behaviour and influencing factors in handicraft purchasing are positively correlated.

Table 5.3. Regression Coefficient in consumers' age and Consumers' Behaviour to Purchase

Products

Hypothesis	Regression Weights	Beta Coefficient	R	R ²	F	p-value	Hypothesis supported
H2	Age-consumer behaviour	.118	.291	.085	21.54***	.000	Yes

Note. N = 234.

*** $P < .001$.

Hypothesis 2

h₁ Age of consumers positively impacts on consumer behaviour towards purchasing handicraft products.

The above-mentioned hypothesis reveals that consumers' age impacts on their behaviour significantly. Test reveals that the consumer behaviour (dependent variable) was regressed on the predictor variable, consumer age. Consumers' behaviour while buy handicrafts was significantly predicted by their age ($F = 21.54$, $p < 0.001$). The results suggested that age can have its impact on consumers' behaviour significantly ($b = .118$, $p < .001$). The results also suggests that growing age has positive impact with it and Pearson's $R = .291$ shows a weak but significant relationship. In addition, the results reveal the $R^2 = .085$ indicates total 8.5% variance in consumers' behaviour. As the regression coefficient shows a positive correlation so this alternative hypothesis is accepted. Finally, it can be interpreted that if the age of customers increases by one unit, then the significant change in consumer behaviour towards buying handicraft products can be expected and this is a desirable finding for the growth of handicraft sector.

Table 5.4. Assessment the effect of Annual Family Income on consumer's behaviour

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R	R ²	F	p-value	Hypothesis supported
H3	Annual family income-consumer behaviour	4.501E-006	.35	.123	32.46***	.000	Yes

Note. $N = 234$

*** $P < .001$

Hypothesis 3

h₁ Annual family income of consumers positively impacts on consumer behaviour towards purchasing handicraft products.

The hypothesis examined whether a consumer's annual family income positively impacts on their decision to buy handicraft products. To test the hypothesis, the dependent variable, consumer behaviour, was regressed on the independent variable that predicted the consumers' yearly family income. The findings showed that consumers' yearly family income strongly predicted their handicraft-buying behaviour ($F(1, 234) = 32.46, p < 0.001$), indicating that income can have a big impact on customers behaviour. The modest change indicated by the beta coefficient score = $4.501E-006$ (0.000004501), $p < 0.001$ may be due to the fact that income is measured in bigger units, meaning that a one-rupee increase will not affect behaviour. However, a higher income increase would undoubtedly have an impact on consumer behaviour, and Pearson's $R = .35$ indicates a strong but moderately favourable relationship. Additionally, the model explains 12.3% of the variance in customer behaviour, as indicated by the $R^2 = .123$. This alternate hypothesis is adopted since the regression coefficient showed a substantial positive relationship as predicted.

Table 5.5. Average, Standard Deviation, and One-Way ANOVA in Age-Related Consumer Behaviour

Variable	16-22 years		23-28 Years		29-34 Years		35-40 Years		F (3, Post-230)	Hoc
	N = 81		N = 96		N = 49		N = 8			
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Consumer behaviour	9.85	2.08	11.06	2.28	11.43	3.01	13.25	1.58	8.73***	4>3>2>1

*** $p < .001$.

Table 5 describes differences in consumer behaviour to purchase handicrafts based on their age with use of F test. Age of consumers is divided in total four categories for age 16 to 40 years of age. The above findings help to understand which category of youth is more interested in handicrafts. The age of respondents is categorised as given in Table 5, which shows the significant mean differences among each age category on consumer behaviour with $F(3, 230) = 8.73, p < 0.001$. The data revealed that the age group 35- 40 years adopted a higher level of positive behaviour that is cleared with mean score (14.25) towards purchasing handicraft products as compared to other given age categories 16-22 years, 23-28 years and 29–34 years of age. Tukey's post-hoc comparison test is used for more clarity into the variations among each age group. The difference in mean scores of given each age group is significant from the other three groups. Silver (2012) also found notable variations in consumer behaviour according to age.

The significant impact of age on the buying behaviour of handicraft products could be attributed to several factors such as generational preferences, cultural and social influences, emotional connection, marketing strategies, personal milestones, perceived value, education and awareness.

Table 5.6 Difference in Consumer Behaviour based on Annual Family Income

Variable	Below 1 Lac		1 Lac–3 Lac		3 Lac-5 Lac		Above 5 Lac		F (3, 230)	Post-Hoc
	N = 16		N = 67		N = 52		N = 99			
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Consumer behaviour	10.00	2.28	9.66	2.61	10.79	2.00	11.70	2.31	10.81***	4>3>2>1

*** $p < .001$.

The above given table 6 reveals the difference in consumer behaviour and their annual family income. The income was divided in 4 categories as below one lac, one lac to three lac, three lac to five lac, and over five lac rupees based on the data received. The results notably finds that a considerable difference in consumers' annual family income demonstrated by $F = 10.81, p < .001$.

The consumers with having over 5 Lac annual family income demonstrated higher positive behaviour than the other consumers' income groups that is suggested by the mean= 11.70. Tukey's post-hoc comparisons reveals that the difference among mean values of each income group is significant. Silver (2012) also mentioned a notable change in consumer behaviour based on their income.

There could be a feasible cause behind this that the factors as mentioned in this paper opinion of others, aesthetic value, functional value, social status, uniqueness and trends of handicraft plays important role with changes in economic status to formulate consumers' behaviour.

6.0 DISCUSSION

The findings of the study indicated positive consumer behaviour towards purchasing handicraft products. Young consumers with highly positive attitudes towards sustainable handicrafts are likely to adopt these products, thereby contributing to the revival of sustainable handicrafts. The majority of respondents demonstrated a favourable attitude towards purchasing these items. Krishnaraj et al. (2022) also reported positive consumer behaviour regarding the purchase of palm leaf-made handicrafts. Research on the key factors influencing young consumers' behaviour in this area suggested that significant variables could potentially modify purchasing practices. Liu et al. (2024) found that the artisans should focus on the products' designs in increasing market demand. Additionally, consumers consider the product's functionality, aesthetic value (as noted by Rani and Banis, 2014), quality, and price. These elements can lead to an increase in consumer interest in handicrafts. Pani and Pradhan (2016); Silver and Kundu (2012) found a significant relationship between consumer opinions on appearance and status and their purchasing behaviour. While Pani and Pradhan (2016) indicated that the consumers' age does not significantly influence consumer preference but this study observed that age was indeed crucial in shaping consumer behaviour.

Silver and Kundu (2012); Safi et al. (2021) also identified a significant relationship between demographic factors like age and income, and purchasing behaviour. The notable impact of age on purchasing handicraft products can be attributed to various factors, such as generational preferences, cultural and social influences, emotional connections, marketing strategies, personal milestones, perceived value, education, and awareness. Prajapati and Uraon (2024) found that income had a significant influence on the purchasing of traditional handicrafts. This impact may be due to the dominance of personal preferences, cultural values, social status, product quality, uniqueness, functional values, and fashion trends in influencing consumer behaviour related to income variations. Ultimately, this leads to growth in the handicraft sector, prompting artisans to create more attractive and fashionable products that appeal to young consumers, encouraging them to support sustainable handicrafts. Sandhu (2022) suggested that the adoption of new techniques and methods could provide opportunities to sustain the culture of handicrafts. Agarwal and Gautam (2021) also revealed that online selling is a good opportunity for marketing of handicraft products. Additionally, Safi et al. (2021) found that young consumers are more open to innovations in handicraft products.

CONCLUSION

Majorly Handicraft products are eco-friendly and sustainable and have no harmful effect on environment. In present study, young consumers were participated, which dictated the constituent that inspire them to buy handicrafts. The results describes that opinion of friends and family have bigger impact on regulation of their decision in purchasing followed by the utility of products. Moreover, the findings reveal that consumers buy handicrafts to show their aesthetic values and to maintain their social standard. Consumer behaviour for buying handicrafts increases as their age and income increase. Artisans should design the products based on the need of consumers' age

based. Young consumers have positive attitude for the usage of sustainable, eco-friendly handicraft items. Their next generation might aware about the importance of these handicraft products after having education by the consumers who have positive perception on it. They can aware them about the representation of handicrafts as a part of Indian culture and tradition of handicrafts. Young consumers are more often familiar with digital platforms. They might spread new viewpoints and creative concepts about the handicraft industry, along with their keenness for helping out regional artisans and preserving traditional craft. The study suggests that artisans should make products in accordance of consumers' preferences, need and current trends.

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